

THE CORRELATION OF INSTAGRAM USAGE AND STUDENTS' ENGLISH PROFICIENCY: SMAN 1 MARTAPURA FOR CLASS XII 1 AND 29

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Abstract: Instagram has always been popular among the youth and collectively, this creates a large community with various content from entertainment to education. This study aimed to examine whether students' Instagram usage could serve as a predictor of students' English proficiency at a high school in Martapura. This study employed a quantitative correlation research design to analyze the relationship between English proficiency through in grade 11 and their usage of Instagram through online survey questionnaire. The results of the Pearson correlation coefficient collected through IBM SPSS 27 showed that the students' use of Instagram was negatively correlated with their average daily Instagram usage (in daily hours), based on data from 31 participants in SMA Negeri 1 Martapura. Although, in the end, Instagram did not have a correlation with English proficiency, it can still function greatly as a learning tool when used properly. Therefore, by providing bilingual education and using social media applications properly of both English and Indonesian language and implementing English during childhood can not only improve their language capabilities but also broaden the use from communicating to creating international business opportunity.

Keywords: English proficiency, Social media, technology, usages, Instagram usage

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rampant integration of social media into daily life has significantly influenced various aspects of education, notably language acquisition. Social media has become integral to daily life, influencing various aspects of society, including education and language acquisition. Using platforms, commonly Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, TikTok, WeChat, and so on, offered users unprecedented exposure to diverse languages and cultures. This phenomenon is particularly relevant in non-native English-speaking regions like Martapura, where social media may be a supplementary tool for enhancing English proficiency such as reading skills. (Song & Xiong, 2023; Bjornsson, 2023)

With technology, enhancing fluency and proficiency altogether has been successful in the works of D. (2024) where the study concludes with an improvement of 11% using TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning) on students. Studies on technology-based learning using different teaching methods have shown to be effective such as Nafea's (2024) study on undergraduates in Bangladesh successfully integrating technology for language instructions as long as the educators were proficient in using the tools and Pupitasari and Pelawi (2023) have also concluded in their study in Indonesia that teaching the English Language with technology can provide better practices found digitally and providing effective self-studying.

Social media usage has both positive and negative impacts on people's lives. While studies have found negative effects such as social anxiety, motivation, distraction, and low self-esteem, most researchers have found that it still influences language learning, particularly in English, particularly in vocabulary, reading, and writing skills. This is due to constant reading and typing, including visual representations of what is being described. While social media may not fully contribute to language proficiency, it does have an impact on vocabulary, writing, and reading comprehension. (Alshalawi, 2022; Arbain M. , Ramadani, Novika, Hasbi, & Perdana, 2024; Giunchiglia, Zeni, Gobbi, Bignotti, & Bison, 2020; Bjornsson, 2023; Nasution, 2022)

Instagram is a well-known and one of the most used application when it comes to social media usages around the world for people's daily life consuming most of their lives. Posts, stories, and reels are some of the main features of Instagram and culture, students, both young and old, can participate in learning using the apps through the engagement and creativity that allows the student to view from content creators. In the works of Thomas et al. (2020), there have been 1-3 hours of usage each day from their respondents by the "youths", as described, to have less motivation to engage in educational content and accounts and instead wants to be more presentable in the mainstream that follows them to gain more followers. But with their educational account, there were 43% of followers continued to remain for the study participation.

Regardless of the disadvantages, there are still many benefits that social media usage can offer, and among those are exposure, authenticity, engagement, and collaborative and resource sharing creating a safe environment to dive into existing or create new ways to learn language effectively and efficiently. (Muftah, 2022; Islam, 2022; Desta, Workie, Yemer, Denku, & Berhanu, 2021)

The potential for Instagram to be a tool for education are said to be high due to its satisfaction and engagement that were not offered by regular lectures and teaching tool typically affecting Generation Z and later. (Thomas, Chavez, & Minnis, 2020; Obeso, Pérez, Piqueres, & Bedia, 2023) But a study by Pekpazar et al. (2021) have found that it can instead lead to procrastination in learning affecting their studies and creating a social media addiction from the survey they conducted. But nevertheless, the relationship between studies and the addiction are factored from their procrastination

1.1. Research Questions

With researchers proving that social media can either have negative and positive impacts, social media apps can play a role in our daily lives and learning capabilities. So will there be any positive significant correlation between students' English proficiency and their Instagram usage?

1.2. Research Objective

Moreover, social media usage can affect either negatively or positively and thus the main objective is to find whether their English proficiency correlates with their social media usage when encountering English medium content.

1.3. Hypothesis

The null hypothesis (H_0) states that there is no positive significant correlation between students' Instagram usage and their English proficiency among 11th-grade students at SMA Negeri 1 Martapura. This suggests that variations in students' social media engagement do not have a meaningful impact on their ability to use and understand English. Any observed relationship between these two variables is likely due to random chance rather than a true connection.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_a) asserts that there is a significant correlation between social media usage and English proficiency among 11th-grade students at SMA Negeri 1 Martapura. This implies that students who engage more with social media may exhibit different levels of English proficiency compared to those who use it less. The relationship between these variables is expected to be strong enough to suggest that social media usage plays a role in shaping students' English language skills.

1.4. Significances

Students' usage of social media has affected their learning in many ways and this research aims to provide insight into teenagers' influence from social media and understand their familiarity when using social media as a way to learn the English language. Additionally by raising awareness of how many students had scored higher or lower in their English scores in the city of Martapura.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Social Media for EFL Learning

Since social media has grown largely at an international rate, people have been affected in both good and bad. Giunchiglia, et al. (2020), Bjornsson (2023), Nasution (2022), Chen and Xiao (2022), and Shu (2023), to name a few have found struggles and disadvantages stemming from social media usages that negatively comprises social anxiety, motivation, distraction, negative time management, low esteem, etc. were discussed but the majority of researchers had mentioned in their works that it still influenced language learning, especially in English, specifically in vocabulary, reading, writing skills since they would read and type constantly including visual representations of what would be described. Social media may not contribute to the complete proficiency of a language but influences on vocabulary, writing, and reading comprehension exist. (Umirov, 2023; Alshalawi, 2022; Giunchiglia, Zeni, Gobbi, Bignotti, & Bison, 2020; Arbain M. , Ramadani, Novika, Hasbi, & Perdana, 2024)

2.2. Negative Impacts of Social Media

A negative effect when learning languages using SM is information overload. Despite the vast accessibility of language learning, it is also hard to pin point accurate and reliable resources stemming from outdated information and inaccuracy in languages from olden and unused slangs. Moreover, students in particular can get distracted from learning due to many activities available in the vast sea of internet. (Umirov, 2023)

Furthermore, Alshalawi (2022) has had reviewed many journals and other studies pertaining social media usage in learning and stated that there were some

negative perceptions about SMNs (Social Media Networks) where it talks that it lacks credibility, privacy, time consumption, and complexity which were similar to what previously said by other scholars. Additionally, some SM apps that were built specifically for communications like Facebook had an awkward experience for students when learning especially when it involves tutors. But from the result of the study, there were more positive receptions and results.

2.3. Positive Impacts of Social Media

Alshalawi (2022) mentioned how over two dozen of studies that were reviewed had resulted in positive impact for students when using SM in learning. Nine out of 28 studies were found either neutral or negative, the study resulted in 19 studies showing positive impact for learning using SM. The study concluded that SMNs are recommended for further learning and integration in teaching. And method of adopting SMNs or SMs is crucial and therefore the author mentioned the value of how reviewing studies made by integrating SMNs can be helpful in this modern era in learning.

Social media serve also as authentic language resources that can be effectively integrated into the EFL classroom to enhance student motivation and support the creation of engaging, enjoyable learning activities. They offer a dynamic and realistic environment for language acquisition by exposing learners to real-world language use, including vocabulary, writing comprehension, slang, colloquialisms, and contemporary cultural trends. Platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook foster linguistic creativity by enabling students to produce multimedia content and infographics. Additionally, social media use contributes to the development of students' digital literacy, equipping them with skills to assess online information critically, practice appropriate digital behavior, and navigate various digital platforms confidently. Furthermore, social media support multimodal learning by combining visual, auditory, and textual elements, accommodating diverse learning preferences and enhancing overall language comprehension. (Mitrulescu, 2024; Bjornsson, 2023)

For the enhancement of English skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing, the study by Abdullah (2024), concluded similarly with more active participants view the use of SM to be effective with many positive views from learning ESL (English as a Second Language) by constantly using it, stress-free environment for learning language, access to authentic languages, becoming self-confident, and many more. This further proves from the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test where the language skills were tested and showed that reading skill scored 13.28 over 9.7 in listening while writing skill scored 15.98 over 10.30 in listening. Between listening skills and pronunciations, pronunciations scores higher at 15.44 over 12.25 showing another difference. As for speaking skills, pronunciation had still ranked higher than speaking skills with 15.30 over 11.58 respectively. Grammar knowledge had more significance over listening. Writing skills in addition had higher score than speaking. In summary, many visual input that were made had higher mean score over listening and practical output excluding pronunciation.

Instagram for Learning

Instagram is a SM application that serves as a powerful medium for engagement, community building, and knowledge dissemination. Through visually appealing posts, story features, and interactive captions, libraries attract students and

enhance their awareness of academic resources. This demonstrates Instagram's potential beyond social interaction turning it into an effective channel for fostering academic curiosity and lifelong learning. (Drivas & Vraimaki, 2024)

In the works of Balani and Jaisinghani (2025) about Instagram usage and education, it is a social media platform that provides a mix of entertainment, motivational, and educational content, with its impact on students differing based on individual usage and context. The study conducted an investigated the influence of Instagram usage on academic performance among students preparing for competitive exams and the research revealed that Instagram was predominantly used in the evening and late-night hours, often replacing study time. Although the statistical data did not show a direct correlation with both positive and negative impact between Instagram usage and students' exams, the findings emphasized that excessive usage could disrupt consistent study patterns. This highlights the importance of moderation and intentional use of social media platforms to avoid interference with academic responsibilities.

2.4. Language Acquisition through Instagram Exposure

Instagram for countries that uses multiple languages such as Indonesia, with over 700 languages, often combines Indonesian language or Indonesian dialects with English. This combination or blend of different languages are called code-mixing. People's exposure to the English language in Instagram can contribute to the influence of code-mixing through their vocabulary that would often be caused by scrolling through posts, captions, reels, etc. in which other people would use. Most notably influencers having a major influence in code-mixing throughout social media applications and especially Instagram. (Zabua, Munthe, Manik, & Suprayetno, 2025) The study about code-switching implied that it can be beneficial in creating connections with cultures outside Indonesia's own culture and paving the way to embrace understanding through communication.

Hamid et al. (2025) investigated how consistent exposure to short video content on Instagram Reels impacts students' English listening comprehension. The study observed 103 university EFL learners who engaged with English-language Reels daily over a two-month period. Results demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in students' listening test scores, especially in recognizing informal speech patterns, pronunciation variations, and contextual understanding. Reels, which often include subtitles, humor, and culturally relevant expressions, exposed learners to authentic and varied English usage. The research emphasized the role of passive learning and multimodal input—audio combined with visual context—in enhancing comprehension. Students also reported increased motivation and reduced anxiety when learning from Reels compared to traditional classroom methods. While some content lacked grammatical accuracy, the overall exposure contributed positively to familiarizing learners with natural speech. The study concluded that Reels can be integrated as a complementary learning tool, though it recommended guiding students in selecting high-quality and educational content.

Sadha, Novitri, and Syarfi (2022) examined the correlation between social media use and the English reading comprehension abilities of English Department students. The researchers analyzed data from 73 students through reading proficiency tests and digital behavior surveys. Findings suggested a moderate positive correlation between times spent engaging with English-language content on social media platforms, especially Instagram and Twitter, and reading ability. Students who

regularly read English captions, blog-style posts, infographics, or subtitles appeared to process syntactic structures and vocabulary more efficiently. The immersive nature of social media allowed them to practice scanning, skimming, and contextual guessing skills frequently. However, the study also noted that students who consumed only visual content without text showed no significant improvement. Interestingly, the researchers emphasized interaction with content, such as reading and replying to English comments, as a key factor in strengthening comprehension. The study proposed integrating social media-based tasks in academic reading classes to encourage habitual engagement with English texts. While not a replacement for formal instruction, social media served as a useful supplementary resource for enhancing reading fluency.

To explain furthermore, the findings revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.622$), with social media usage accounting for 38.7% of the variance in reading performance. The researchers concluded that students who frequently engaged with English-language content on platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter tended to have better reading abilities. This was attributed to increased exposure to diverse vocabulary, sentence structures, and authentic language use. The study emphasized that the type of content consumed played a significant role –students who followed news outlets, educational pages, or English-speaking influencers benefited more than those who consumed only visual or entertainment content. The findings support the notion that passive but frequent exposure to a target language in real contexts can enhance language skills. The study contributes to the growing body of literature affirming the educational potential of social media, particularly in fostering reading comprehension among language learners. It also suggests that integrating social media content into the curriculum could support students' out-of-classroom learning. (Sadha, Novitri, & Syarfi, 2022)

In a study made by Teng et al. (2022), the researchers examined the effect of using Instagram feed-based grammar tasks on students' grammatical proficiency. The participants, consisting of university-level EFL learners, engaged with instructional posts that embedded grammar explanations and exercises directly into Instagram's visual content stream. These posts included short captions, fill-in-the-blank stories, and comment-based peer feedback activities that students interacted with daily over the course of a semester. The results showed that learners exposed to these feed-based grammar tasks demonstrated higher retention and usage accuracy than those taught using only conventional classroom instruction. This improvement was attributed to the constant exposure to target structures and the bite-sized, repetitive nature of content on Instagram, which reinforces learning through microdoses. Moreover, learners expressed increased motivation and satisfaction due to the platform's informal and visual nature, which contrasted with traditional textbook exercises. The study also highlighted the accessibility of learning where students can review lessons at their own pace and revisit posts any time, fostering autonomous learning. Despite the study's small sample size and context-specific findings, it presents a strong case for integrating social media tools into EFL grammar instruction. The researchers concluded that social platforms like Instagram could be used not just for content delivery, but also as participatory spaces where learners co-construct grammar knowledge. This aligns with constructivist learning theory, suggesting that language proficiency can be meaningfully supported through learner-centered, technology-enhanced environments.

Damanik (2022) conducted a correlational study to examine the relationship between Instagram usage and vocabulary mastery among English Education

students at Universitas Negeri Malang. The study involved 129 participants and utilized both a structured questionnaire to measure the frequency and intensity of Instagram usage and a standardized vocabulary size test to assess students' vocabulary knowledge. Surprisingly, the study revealed a very weak and non-significant correlation ($r = -0.127$) between Instagram use and vocabulary mastery. This suggests that students' general use of Instagram did not contribute meaningfully to the expansion of their English vocabulary. The researcher noted that students might not be actively engaging with English content on Instagram, as many preferred entertainment and lifestyle posts in their native language. Damanik recommended that future studies narrow the focus to those who follow or interact with English-learning accounts or educational pages. Furthermore, the study emphasized the importance of intentional learning behavior over passive scrolling. Despite its insignificant findings, the research sheds light on the nuanced role of social media in language learning. It suggests that not all Instagram usage translates into linguistic gain unless it is purposefully directed. Overall, the study contributes to understanding how learner motivation and content engagement mediate the influence of digital platforms on vocabulary acquisition.

2.5. Perceptions of Instagram as an EFL Learning language by the Students

In a systematic literature review by Nasution (2023) on English language learning, the author explained that Instagram can also foster enhanced vocabulary acquisition, grammar understanding, writing development, and learner collaboration for the student through the platform's visual and interactive features such as story posts, comments, reels, and direct messages creating a multimodal learning environment where students engage more creatively and meaningfully creating an informal atmosphere encouraging active participation and continuous language exposure, making it an effective complement to formal learning settings. Learners were more engaged and motivated through its multimodal features like images and videos which effectively increased their motivation and provided less strain in learning the English language. The review concluded that Instagram effectively enhances language learning outcomes by fostering creativity and learner autonomy. This also correlates with other works by Abdullah (2024), Mitrulescu (2024), and Bjornsson (2023) to name a few about benefits of Instagram as a SM platform to learn languages. However, Nasution (2023) also advised mindful use, as excessive distraction could hinder deeper learning.

In another study by Alghanmi and Madini (2025) through exploring Saudi university students' perceptions of Instagram Reels in language acquisition, the findings showed that short-form videos, also known as Reels, on Instagram contributed positively to vocabulary development, pronunciation accuracy, and spoken fluency. Students reported that engaging with Reels created by native and proficient English speakers provided real-life context and modeled authentic language use. Additionally, the interactive comments and peer feedback encouraged learners to experiment with speaking and writing in English. The study concluded that Instagram Reels serve as an effective tool for enhancing speaking and listening skills in an immersive, enjoyable format.

In a study conducted by Handayani and Pratiwi (2023), they examined the perceptions of vocational high school students in Bandar Lampung regarding Instagram's influence on their vocabulary mastery. Through a descriptive qualitative approach, the study found that most students had a favorable opinion of using

Instagram as an informal learning platform. Notably, over 75% of the participants believed that creating English captions for their Instagram posts contributed significantly to their vocabulary expansion. Furthermore, around 40% strongly agreed that interacting with English-language content, such as comments, hashtags, and influencer posts, increased their exposure to practical and contextual vocabulary. Students also mentioned that they felt more confident using new words in both written and spoken English after regularly engaging with Instagram. The integration of technology into daily habits appeared to boost motivation and language awareness, especially in a relaxed, social setting. While the study did not include a formal vocabulary test, self-reported experiences implied a perceived correlation between Instagram use and language development. Participants viewed Instagram not only as a communication tool but also as a resource for learning through observation and imitation. The researchers concluded that leveraging popular digital platforms could enhance students' enthusiasm for vocabulary learning outside conventional classrooms. This aligns with broader trends of integrating digital literacy into language education.

When students were encouraged to share learning reflections, vocabulary posts, or English stories through Instagram, they became more independent and responsible in their language learning journey. Instagram acted as a self-directed learning platform that provided learners with ownership and freedom, while still maintaining social interactivity. It successfully bridged formal instruction with informal, self-motivated learning practices. This shows that Instagram can foster learner autonomy through self-paced and interest-based content exploration. Using Instagram to follow English learning pages, participate in challenges, and share their learning experiences, which helped build self-confidence. The platform also allowed learners to set personal goals and track their improvement. The study concluded that Instagram can be a valuable tool for promoting independent learning, provided learners are digitally literate and maintain a balance between leisure and learning. (Putra & Madkur, 2025)

Another qualitative study conducted by Fitri and Maghfiroh (2024) explored how Instagram users perceive the platform's effectiveness in supporting vocabulary learning. The study involved 35 active Instagram users who engaged with English content through features like feeds, stories, and reels. Based on interviews and observation, the researchers found that participants generally believed Instagram made vocabulary learning more engaging and less intimidating. Many users reported that seeing new words repeatedly in different contexts such as memes, captions, and language-learning pages and this helped them remember those words more easily. The visual nature of Instagram was credited for improving word association and recall. Additionally, participants shared that using Instagram increased their curiosity to search for word meanings and proper usage, especially when they encountered unfamiliar terms. Several respondents noted that following English-learning accounts or influencers who spoke in English motivated them to adopt similar vocabulary in daily communication. While the study relied on subjective data, the results strongly suggested that Instagram plays a supportive role in vocabulary acquisition by creating a low-pressure, context-rich learning environment. The participants viewed Instagram as both an entertaining and educational tool, especially when usage was intentional. Ultimately, this research adds to the growing evidence that learners perceive social media as a valuable supplement to traditional language learning.

2.6. Critical Thinking

Zalani and Yousofi (2024) study further shows that Instagram can also give positive result in learning as they conducted a study in which students who were from two groups, an experimental group (who received Instagram-integrated instruction) and a control group (who learned using traditional classroom methods). The experimental group engaged with structured tasks delivered via Instagram, including reading prompts, discussion questions, and multimedia-based analysis activities. After several weeks, participants took the California Critical Thinking Skills Test, where the Instagram group scored significantly higher than their peers. This suggests that carefully designed social media instruction can enhance not just engagement but also deeper analytical abilities, an essential skill for mastering complex language tasks. Students reported that Instagram made learning feel more relevant and interactive, aligning with modern communication styles they were already familiar with. This familiarity likely reduced cognitive load, allowing learners to focus more on critical engagement with content. Although limitations include the specific cultural and age context of Iranian learners, the study supports the broader pedagogical value of social media when guided by instructional design. Ultimately, the research offers compelling evidence that Instagram, when used intentionally, can facilitate not just social interaction, but also academically meaningful skills that support English proficiency indirectly.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative correlation research design similar to Gonulal's (2019) and Zalani and Yousofi's (2024) research to analyze the relationship between English proficiency through grades and their usage of Instagram through online survey questionnaire adapted from Gonulal's (2019) work.

3.2. Research Setting

The predictor variable is social media usage which was measured through self-reported surveys about platforms, frequency of usage, and views.

The criterion variable is the English proficiency which was be measured using students' scores from EF SET.

3.4. Population and Sample of Research

The two classes from grade 11, XI-1 and XI-2 were selected 30 from each class, with a total population of 60 participants, in SMAN 1 Martapura using a purposive sampling technique.

3.5. Technique of Data Collecting

Survey questionnaires were sent through Google Forms link to the students containing questions about their social media and Instagram platform preferences, frequency of usages, views, etc. This helped the research in analyzing patterns and trends related to their engagement with social media.

English proficiency data were also obtained through students', with the collaboration of the head class, to collect the English scores from EF Standard

English Testing (EFSET) of 50 minutes as an indicator of proficiency. This standardized test will serve as an indicator of their English language skills, providing a reliable basis for evaluating their proficiency in relation to their social media usage.

3.6. Technique of Data Analysis

Descriptive data analysis and correlation analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics 27 were utilized to measure the strength of the relationship between variables. Significance testing will be conducted to determine the presence of a correlation through the usage of the Pearson-product moment correlation.

3.7. Statistical Hypothesis

Social Media has always been useful in learn and applying variety of methods to not only study language but also many other fields that involved social media and Instagram, namely Alghanmi and Madini (2025) and Zalani and Yousofi (2024), showed improvement with a positive impact in their English language learning. Social media, an influence of technology, which can be used as a learning medium has many ways, to affect the populace both good and bad depending on the implementation. Proper implementation of SM that were used to teach English had an advantage to learn English as was proven by Abdullah (2024) and Zalani and Yousofi (2024) to name a few where the majority of the studies and other work showed more improvement in vocabulary, reading, and writing skills.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Students that conducted the test and survey showed that 32 students were selected and out of the 32 students, one participant did not use Instagram, and therefore, one participant was excluded and tallied up to only 31 students. The majority uses a mix of Instagram, Youtube, Twitter, Tiktok, and including few that uses WhatsApp, discord, Google, Clearnote, and Wattpad as a social media platform as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Used Social Media Applications

The descriptive statistics for English proficiency scores and daily Instagram usage are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of English Score and Instagram Hours

		English_Score	Insta_Hours
N	Valid	31	31
	Missing	0	0
Mean		40.74	1.8387
Median		38.00	1.5000
Mode		27 ^a	1.00
Std. Deviation		13.626	1.06956
Skewness		.781	.934
Std. Error of Skewness		.421	.421
Minimum		24	.50
Maximum		75	4.00

The mean of the English proficiency score was $M = 40.74$ or 41 if we round it off, and in regards to CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) for languages, it is at least A2 (elementary) or at best B1 (Intermediate) on average.

The standard deviation for English scores is 13.63, which shows that students' scores vary widely around the average of 40.74. This means that many students scored quite differently—some much higher or lower than the average.

The median score for English scores were 38 which is an A2 level and the mode is 27 or A1. Scores ranged from 24 (A1) to 75 (C2). The distribution showed positive skewness (skewness = 0.781, SE = 0.421), indicating a higher concentration of students scoring below the mean.

The standard deviation for Instagram usage is 1.08 hours, which means students' daily usage is closer to the average of 1.83 hours. Most students spent about 1–2 hours per day, with only a few using Instagram a lot more or less. With a median of 1.50 hours and a mode of 1.00 hour. Usage ranged from less than a day per week to around 5 hours day at most. The data also indicated a positively skewed distribution (skewness = 0.903), meaning most students used Instagram for less time than the average. These findings suggest that while English proficiency varies substantially, most students tend to use Instagram for 1 to 2 hours per day, with few heavy users.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Majority had scored B2 with 10 students and A1 with 9 students. The average hours spent on Instagram is 1.84 hours. The average score for B2 was 47.8 and students that reached A1 had scored on average 26.67. Two out of 32 participants had reached C2 level at 75 and 72 scores and oddly enough, one uses Instagram more or less 4 hours while the other uses it for an hour respectively according to the survey conducted. This large difference shows that attaining C2 level does not positively or even correlate to the usage of Instagram everyday as shown that other students had also used Instagram from less than an hour to 5 hours daily as demonstrated in Table 2.

Table 2: English Scores and Instagram Hours

NO	English Scores	Hour Usage	Midpoint hours
1	A1 - 24	2 hours	2
2	A1 - 25	Depends on the needs +-2	2
3	A1 - 25	More or less 4 hours	4
4	A1 - 26	2 - 4 hours	3
5	A1 - 27	Less than 3 hours	2.75
6	A1 - 27	2 hours	2
7	A1 - 27	More or less 2 hours	2
8	A1 - 29	1-2 hours	1.5
9	A1 - 30	More or less 1 hour	1
10	A2 - 31	4	4
11	A2 - 32	1-2 hours	1.5
12	A2 - 32	1 hour	1
13	A2 - 32	More or less 1 hour	1
14	A2 - 33	1 to 2 hours	1.5
15	A2 - 35	Less than 3 hours	2.75
16	A2 - 38	2 hours	2
17	B1 - 45	1 hour	1
18	B1 - 45	1 hour	1
19	B1 - 46	30 minutes	0.5
20	B1 - 47	3-5 hours	4
21	B1 - 48	Less than 2 hours	1.75
22	B1 - 48	1 hours	1
23	B1 - 49	2-3 hours	2.5
24	B1 - 50	Would not reach 1. Just checking normally	0.75
25	B1 - 50	1 hour	1
26	B1 - 50	<1 jam	0.75
27	B2 - 52	2 jam	2
28	B2 - 53	1 jam	1
29	B2 - 60	With mood, wouldn't reach 1 hour	0.75
30	C2 - 72	1 hour	1
31	C2 - 75	+- 4 hours	4

During the correlation analysis, a Pearson product-moment correlation was conducted to examine the relationship between students' English proficiency scores and their average daily Instagram usage (in daily hours), based on data from 31 participants. The usage of the t-table (two tailed) was used to understand and find whether it was significant or not. The results indicated a weak negative correlation, $r(29) = -0.179$, $p = 0.335$. This correlation was not statistically significant since the significance was 0.335 which are higher than the alpha level of 0.05 hence the negative correlation and therefore accepts the null hypothesis (H_0). These findings suggest that while there is a slight tendency for higher Instagram usage to be associated with lower English proficiency, the relationship is too weak and non-significant to draw any meaningful conclusions. This is demonstrated in both Table 3 and Figure 2.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis for English Scores and Instagram Hours

		English_Score	Insta_Hours
English_Score	Pearson Correlation	1	-.179
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.335
	N	31	31
Insta_Hours	Pearson Correlation	-.179	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.335	
	N	31	31

Figure 2: Scatter Plot diagram

4.3. Subskill Analysis: Reading and Listening

During the process of data collection, 21 students out of the 32 had managed to provide proper scores for their result which included reading and listening as shown in Table 4. The mean for reading is 46.9 while listening is 39. Median for reading is 38 and listening is 35. Oddly enough, the mode for reading is 28 which is much lower than the listening on 34. This shows that majority have higher listening skills despite the higher reading average. But regardless, the average scores for reading was much higher than listening with 81 compared to 71 respectively.

Table 4: English Scores with Reading and Listening Scores

NO	English Scores	Reading	Listening
1	A1 - 26	21	30
2	A1 - 27	28	25
3	A1 - 30	31	29
4	A1 - 30	28	31
5	A2 - 31	28	33

6	A2 - 32	30	34
7	A2 - 32	37	27
8	A2 - 33	30	36
9	A2 - 35	37	32
10	A2 - 38	32	43
11	B1 - 45	55	34
12	B1 - 46	58	34
13	B1 - 48	53	43
14	B1 - 48	38	57
15	B1 - 49	62	35
16	B1 - 50	57	43
17	B1 - 50	62	38
18	B2 - 53	68	38
19	B2 - 60	71	49
20	C2 - 72	72	71
21	C2 - 75	87	62

4.4. Languages used in Instagram

With no surprise, 25 participants had chosen Indonesian/first language as their main use of language for their account whereas 7 students uses English in the questionnaire. Considering that the English language is less prevalent in Indonesia, it is more often considered as that is their main language including Banjarese as their first language in South Kalimantan. 17 students uses Banjarese as their main language when communicating which is expected as they are born and raised in Martapura. 10 participants have said to use both first language and English as their most often used language when communicating which suggests that there is some level of mixing between both languages together when communicating.

4.5. Student Perception of Instagram for English Learning

Using the Likert scale (1932), this research determined the perception of the students regarding Instagram and their usage for education and learning EFL. During the survey, all 32 participants had views compelling that Instagram can be used as an application to benefit from learning English as EFL with majority voting 4 out 6, which is considered as agreeable as a decent application for learning English. But with engagement and motivation through speaking and writing, they completely agree that it as a great application for English as a content and for learning respectively.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Limitation

The largest limitation of this study is the response rate. Out of 60 students invited to participate, only 32 provided complete and usable responses, resulting in a response rate of approximately 53.3% and 31 used Instagram which is the main focus for this research. The students who did not participate may differ in meaningful ways from those who did, such as in their English proficiency levels and social media usage patterns. Therefore, the results should be interpreted with caution, as they may not fully represent the behaviors or experiences of the entire target population.

The study followed a midpoint approximation method that is commonly used in survey-based research when dealing with ranges or vague responses. The midpoint approach helps transform qualitative data into quantitative variables suitable for statistical analysis with consideration as such to fit the criteria of the students' hourly Instagram usage. Determining the midpoint can differ for each person in regards of weekly or even daily and thus, each value were set as an approximated point in consideration for their daily usages as shown in Table 2.

Although the total participants in the study was 31, only 21 students provided a complete data set for both reading and listening sections of the proficiency test. Therefore, the sub-skill analysis was based on this smaller dataset.

Additionally, the voluntary nature of participation may have had some conflict in their schedule due to the time of data collection during which the students had projects and cultural events occurring at the time of collecting. Moreover, students with stronger opinions or more interest in the topic may have been more likely to respond, potentially skewing the results.

5.2. Correlation

Just as researched by Balani and Jaisinghani (2025) and Damanik (2022), the results showed negative to no significant correlation in hourly usage of Instagram due to inconsistent timely usage, including other applications used, and their English proficiency. Social media in general can be a positive impact as demonstrated in many works such as seen in other works by Abdullah (2024), Alshalawi (2022), and Mitulescu (2024). But due to the differences in applications, timely usages in multiple SM applications including Instagram, CEFR level, and preferred language usage, many participants had an A1 to A2 level results for their CEFR fluency which goes to show that it has negative correlation from Diagram 3 as demonstrated. This negative correlation further corresponds to Damanik's (2022) when attaining knowledge in English proficiency as their Instagram usages did not contribute entirely to their English language acquisition.

Moreover, the negative correlation can stem due to many factor as per observation during the time of PLP 2 (Pengenalan Lapangan Persekolahan) from October to November. The emphasis on self-confidence as discussed by Shadieff and Wang (2022) Abdullah (2024), Sweet et al. (2025), and Mai et al (2024) can impact learning English due to their surroundings and Sweet et al (2025) and Mai et al (2024) proved that to be the case due to the environment affecting their learning potential, along with their lack of practice, teachers' attendance, self-confidence, and authentic sources in the school contributed to their low level English skills but not for a few.

In reading and listening department, many had shown higher reading capabilities. This proves that attaining reading skills had been more affective as the research by Abdullah (2024) suggests due to the nature of writing, captions, descriptions, and other text based written in SM in general. Although the average for listening was less, majority of the population had higher listening scores, this also further demonstrates that can be slightly effective in contributing listening skills but only by a small margin.

5.3. Questionnaire

Although the correlation were insignificant, the implication that Instagram can still be considered as a functional and useful tool to study the English language. Many agreed and that anyone can find interest in learning EFL as shown through diagram 4 and but with proper attention and enactments throughout their studying and usage of the application. (Nasution, 2023; Andujar, Salaberri-Ramiro, & Martinez, 2020; Shadiev & Wang, 2022) Most participants agreed that Instagram can be used for engagement as it is typically used as a SM platform.

Furthermore, when students were asked what language they would use during communication, 10 students had chosen both English and Indonesian or first language. This suggests a level of code-mixing that is in line with Zabua et al. (2025) research since it described how even in Indonesia, some level of English vocabulary has been used through communication, posts, reels, and even in stories within Instagram. Often times being exposed in the internet, can even help attaining linguistic acquisition in both Instagram and other social media applications as were mentioned by Balani and Jaisinghani (2025) and Alghanmi and Madini (2025).

6. Conclusion

English language in SM has been a prevalent part in the 21st century and an important tool in our integral part of society. From communication, education, engagement, and many more has been used throughout SM platforms in one way or another. Most researchers regarded SM platforms and applications as useful tools on providing positive impact in learning and learning languages if used and applied correctly. Results had shown that there is a negative correlation between English proficiency in high school students in Martapura and Instagram usage. But due to the views of students, in majority agreed, that Instagram can be a great tool for learning and motivation for English and also learning other categories in other field.

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